

FAIR metrics for Earth & Environmental Sciences - preliminary results

In the following, we present an attempt to define specific FAIR metrics for the earth and environmental sciences. In the following, we present an attempt to define specific FAIR metrics for the earth and environmental sciences. This is based on an attempt to capture the current FAIR practices of this community as well as possible and to identify those FAIR practices that are essential for the community from the commonalities found.

We have analyzed FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) from research infrastructures (RIs) and their data provides focussing on Earth & environmental sciences collected within the ENVRI-FAIR, FAIR-IMPACT and FAIR-EASE project.

In addition we have taken into account various documents published by the above mentioned and other relevant EU projects such as GeoInquire and BlueCloud as well as national initiatives such as NFDI4Earth which have performed internal FAIR assessments within their community. These are:

- [D6.2 Report on existing metadata schemes, mappings and converters required both to populate the catalog and for integration with the relevant RIs \[GeoInquire\]](#)
- [MS06 – FAIR-EASE initial evaluation of the FAIRness of digital resources and services \[FAIR-EASE\]](#)
- [D9.9 Marine subdomain FAIRness assessment report \[ENVRI-FAIR\]](#)
- [D11.6: Assessment of FAIRness in the Biodiversity and Ecosystem subdomain \[ENVRI-FAIR\]](#)
- [D2.1 Existing DD&AS and Blue Data Infrastructures – Review and Specifications for Optimisation Report \[Blue-Cloud\]](#)
- [D2.2 Blue Data Infrastructures - Services Analysis Report \[Blue-Cloud\]](#)
- [Recommendations for Earth System Sciences Metadata Provision \[NFDI4Earth\]](#)

Results of the FIP analysis can be found here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1qN0NugAqCSyxwAvNP_YyOLVN7tPID9rFpGPszXwIG00/edit#gid=1378553359

A metadata crosswalk can be found here:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1yPPT0kOXErDo9a-LOh6sP4JjndtKpcTREhPcBvX53aw/edit#gid=0>

In addition some of the most relevant information and data portals for this community such as those of the European Environmental Agency (EEA) or GEOSS have specific requirements for data providers which need to be taken into account.

Based on these information sources we focused on the identification of the community's main FAIR enabling resources. In particular we tried to identify metadata and data standards of common use, metadata properties, discipline specific vocabularies and ontologies, licenses and knowledge representation formats. The following sections summarize the results of these analyses.

Further approaches to defining FAIR metrics from the earth and environmental sciences are currently being pursued by the FAIR-EASE and GeoInquire projects, for example, which may lead to different results for their respective communities. As these approaches have not yet been fully completed at the time of writing this report they are not included in this study. Therefore, the results presented here can only be considered as preliminary results based on an analysis of the current FAIR practices of the community.

Results:

Metadata formats:

We identified a number of metadata standards which are used by all investigated data providers and research infrastructures. Some data providers rely mainly on non-standardized formats and REST APIs. Where metadata standards are used, these organisations provide metadata in either ISO 19115/19139 (incl variants such as ISO19115-2014), EML, DataCite, DCAT or schema.org formats.

Most frequently (12 of 26) metadata are exchanged using ISO 19115/19139 and derivatives (WMO core, EEA profile) or Directory Interchange Format (DIF). The Ecological Modeling Language (EML) format is used by four data providers. Frequently used (7 of 26) are domain-agnostic standards such as DCAT, Dublin Core or schema.org.

The OGC ISO 19115 application profile and related standards are particularly important since these are prescribed by the European legislature, within the INSPIRE directive. Consequently the European Environmental Agency and other European and national governmental bodies rely on these standards. ISO 19115-based standards are also recommended by GEOSS as one of the preferred standards for their portal. NFDI4Earth recommends the use of DCAT (GeoDCAT) or ISO 19115.

Metadata properties

As described in Devaraju & Huber (2021) the FAIRsFAIR metrics implementation of F2 tests the availability of descriptive core metadata properties (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) which are available in most domain-agnostic metadata schemas (see e.g. metadata crosswalk by Wu et al (2022)). In addition to these properties all domain specific metadata standards identified (ISO, EML, DIF etc.) offer dedicated metadata properties to describe the spatial and temporal coverage of an individual dataset. Since this is a common requirement we regard these properties to be essential for the earth

& environmental research community. NFDI4Earth also recommends the inclusion of metadata properties for spatial and temporal coverage along with descriptive properties.

Protocols:

Information collected via FIPs as well as using information from ENVRI, FAIR-EASE, Geolnquire and BlueCloud did not show a clear preference for a distinct set of domain specific metadata or data exchange protocols. Three families of standards which are most frequently used are: DAP (ERDDAP, OPeNDAP, THREDDS; 9 of 26 provider), OGC(CSW, WMS etc) Standards (17 of 26) and OAI-PMH (6 of 26). CSW and OAI-PMH are recommended by NFDI4Earth. Only seven out of the 26 investigated providers do not make use of those three protocol families. From these, biodiversity or -omics related providers strongly rely on custom, OpenAPI REST APIs instead. In summary, it seems as if a consensus on common metadata or data protocols does not exist within the earth & environmental community but most support either OAI-PMH, OGC or DAP protocols. Instead the community relies on generic access protocols such as HTTP, HTTPS or FTP.

Data Formats:

A diverse number of data formats are used by the investigated data providers including image formats (JPG, Geo-TIFF) and scientific formats (such as netCDF or HDF). Most providers use NetCDF (14 of 26) or ASCII/CSV (6 of 26 including DwCA) followed by GeoTIFF (5 of 26) and others. Text based formats such as ASCII or CSV formats (6) or the (zipped) CSV format enclosed in Darwin Core Archives (3) are also frequently used as are RDF or JSON (5) encodings.

While netCDF is often used, no clear preference for this data format can be noticed. Therefore it is not possible to determine file formats which are diagnostic or mandatory for the Earth & Environmental sciences.

Vocabularies:

Not all investigated sources included vocabularies or ontologies, but from those 15 data providers which use vocabularies, eight use those from NERC. Three out of 15 are using the GCMD vocabulary, the GEMET vocabulary is used by three, and ENVThes by two providers. Two data providers, the RIs EPOS and ICOS use their own, custom vocabularies. In summary, use of NERC (marine domain), GCMD, GEMET or ENVThes vocabularies can be taken to be indicative for environmental repositories but no clear preference for these can be noticed. Currently, domain and community specific vocabulary catalogs are built, such as EarthPortal (earthportal.eu) which may serve as a reference for community specific use of ontologies.

Licenses:

Almost all data providers for which we have information (11 of 12 FIPs) on license use are using creative commons licenses. This could be interpreted as some kind of consensus with respect to license choices on the other hand CC licenses are by nature discipline agnostic thus their usage cannot be considered to be a characteristic of the community.

Discipline specific metrics:

Based on our analysis of our subset of the Earth & Environmental Sciences data infrastructure landscape we could only observe few common FAIR implementation practices.

	Common ground
Metadata formats	ISO19119, EML or domain agnostic format which allows to include geographical and temporal coverage information
Metadata properties	creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier, spatial coverage, temporal coverage
Protocols	None
Data Formats	None
Vocabularies	None
Licenses	Creative Commons

Table : Summary of commonly used FAIR implementation practices identified.

These are distinct and common practices regarding the exposure and encoding of discipline specific metadata. We therefore propose to define the following discipline specific FAIR metrics for this community:

2.1 ENV Community Metadata Standard

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-01M-env
Metric Name	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the earth & environmental research community.
Description	<p>In addition to core metadata required to support data discovery (covered under metric FsF-F2-01M), metadata to support data reusability should be made available following community-endorsed metadata standards.</p> <p>For earth & environmental sciences several well established metadata standards exist in particular the family of Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards based on ISO19115 but also other formats are used within the community. Some of these standards are explicitly listed</p> <p>A earth & environmental community repository should support the following standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ISO19115 based format (ISO19139, INSPIRE, EEA, WMO Core) ● Ecological Modelling Language (EML) ● GeoDCAT

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A domain agnostic metadata format which support the inclusion of geospatial and temporal coverage information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DCAT ○ Schema.org ○ DataCite ○ Dublin Core <p>for data set level metadata description.</p>
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL, PID) • Metadata access via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provision endpoints such as SPARQL, CSW, OAI-PMH offering metadata in community specific format ○ Community specific metadata links provided in the landing page via signposting or typed links or via content negotiation. ○ Namespaces listed in community specific documentation or at registries such as FAIRsharing or the RDA metadata standards catalogue
Assessment	Gather all metadata standards used by a data repository; this list can be requested, e.g., from the metadata endpoint (e.g., CSW, SPARQL, OAI-PMH), via namespace URI or XSD URI detection using content retrieved via embedded landing page metadata, signposting links or content negotiation. Identify domain-specific standards (such as ISO19115) from the list specified above.
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/ • ISO/TS 19139-1:2019 Geographic information, https://www.iso.org/standard/67253.html • Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE), https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32007L0002 • EEA Data and metadata requirement guide, https://www.eea.europa.eu/about-us/documents/data-requirement-guide • Boldrini at al. (2023): GEOSS Platform data content and use, https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17538947.2023.2174193 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • *The data identifier provided (e.g., PID) may not be the same as the identifier used in the metadata record harvested. For example, in OAI-PMH, the nature of a record identifier is outside the scope of the harvesting protocol; for more information, see http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html#UniqueIdentifier 	

2.2 ENV Community Metadata Properties (Rich Metadata)

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F2-01M-env

Metric Name	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier as well as spatial and temporal coverage) relevant for the earth & environmental sciences to support data findability.
Description	<p>Metadata is descriptive information about a data object. Since the metadata required differs depending on the users and their applications, this metric focuses on core metadata. The earth & environmental science community has defined specific requirements for core metadata within a series of standards which define metadata schemas and profiles. Most metadata properties covered by these standards coincide to a large extent with domain agnostic specifications such as common data citation guidelines (e.g., DataCite¹, ESIP², and IASSIST³), and metadata recommendations for data discovery (e.g., EOSC Datasets Minimum Information (EDMI)⁴, DataCite Metadata Schema, W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices and Data Catalog Vocabulary). However, in addition also metadata properties which describe the spatial and temporal coverage of an individual dataset are essential for the community and are common in all metadata standards used by the community.</p> <p>Core descriptive metadata for earth & environmental sciences data are <i>creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier as well as spatial and temporal coverage</i>.</p>
FAIR Principle	F2. Data are described with rich metadata
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata
Method	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Parse or retrieve core metadata, e.g., through one or more options below, combine the results and then verify presence/absence of the core elements in the metadata.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Structured data embedded in the landing page of the identifier (e.g., Schema.org or RDFa metadata) ● Typed Links in the HTTP Link header leading to ISO, EML or compatible metadata; for more information, see https://signposting.org/conventions/ ● Content negotiation (including external negotiation services offered by PID providers) to retrieve ISO, EML or other discipline specific metadata or a compatible standard. <p>Check if metadata is available via common methods at all. Check if core descriptive metadata is available.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examples of metadata recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EOSC Interoperability Framework, doi: 10.2777/620649 	

¹ DataCite Metadata Working Group. 2019. "DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3." DataCite e.V. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>.

² ESIP Data Preservation and Stewardship Committee. 2019. "Data Citation Guidelines for Earth Science Data, Version 2." ESIP. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8441816.v1>.

³ <https://iassistdata.org/community/data-citation-ig/data-citation-resources/>

⁴ Asmi, A., B. Cordewener, C. Goble, D. Castelli, E. Kühn, F. Pasion, F. Niccolucci, et al. 2017. "D6.6: 2nd Report on Data Interoperability." EOSCpilot. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5bbdb1165&appId=PPGMS>.

- EOSC EDMI metadata properties, <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>
- W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices, <https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#metadata>
- W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary, <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>
- Metadata crosswalks:
 - Wu et al. (2022) research data schemas to Schema.org : <https://hal.science/hal-03998985/document>
 - Crosswalk of most used metadata schemes: <https://zenodo.org/records/4420116>
- Sites that provide a list of metadata standards:
 - FAIRsharing, <https://fairsharing.org/standards/>
 - RDA Metadata Directory (General Research Data Standards), <https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/subjects/general.html>

Known Limitations/Constraints

- The assessment assumes that the identifier resolves to a landing page (e.g., html) that contains the metadata of the data. Landing page may not necessarily be an html page.
- The metadata records maintained by a data provider might not be accessible, due to, e.g., broken link of the landing page, proprietary metadata standard used, and restricted metadata.